

Methodism in Zimbabwe or Methodist Church in Zimbabwe

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Methodism, Christianity

Methodism in Zimbabwe with particular reference to the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe (MCZ) is one of the largest early denominations in Zimbabwe that has its roots from John Wesley in England. Methodism has unique and distinctive doctrines, rituals, customs and belief systems that are a replica to their pastoral lifestyles. Methodist Church in Zimbabwe has a membership of plus or minus 123 262 members in Zimbabwe (MCZ Handbook 2023:167-168). The development of Methodism in Zimbabwe has its roots in Britain and South Africa who initiated the missionary propagation of the word of God from the North to the South. Today we are witnessing a reverse of the spreading of the gospel where the Southern hemisphere is now going as missionaries to the North to minister in the diaspora. Currently the Zimbabwean Methodist Conference is seconding ministers to work in the diaspora. There is a total membership of 2754 members in diaspora. 339 in Australia, 75 in Botswana, 75 in Canada, 95 in Ireland, 33 in Schengen, 1163 in South Africa, 36 in United Arab Emirates, 853 in United Kingdom and 85 in United States of America (MCZ Agenda of Conference 2023:R61). Taking the example of the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe alone one can deduce that the global south has penetrated the global north. The focus of this study will be from 1891-2023, which represents the time that the first missionaries settled in Zimbabwe and were given the mandate to evangelize and established mission stations in Rhodesia, now Zimbabwe. Geographically, the entry reflects all the areas where Methodist Church in Zimbabwe operate across the spectrum of Zimbabwe and beyond. Methodism in Zimbabwe as shall be noted in the entry operate under the leadership of a Presiding Bishop who is in charge of the whole Zimbabwean Conference. The Zimbabwean Conference constitute eight districts namely: Bulawayo district, Hwange district, Gweru district, Masvingo district, Kadoma district, Marondera district, Harare West district and Harare East district. These districts are under the supervision of a District Bishop who has the responsibility to pastor the district and have an oversight to the whole district. The incumbents are to occupy these positions for a period of 5 years and they go back to the trenches. The succession plan helps the church to be strong and avoid divisions because of the structures that serve the interest of the church at the expense of an individual. The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe is unique and guided by strategic plan that is designed to fulfil its pillars.

Date Range: 1891 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Zimbabwe

Region tags: Zimbabwe, Harare East District, Harare West District, Kadoma District, Hwange District, Marondera District, Masvingo District, Gweru District, Bulawayo District

Zimbabwe is a land locked country which is located in the global South in the sub Saharan region.

Zimbabwe is a unitary, democratic and sovereign state (Constitution of Zimbabwe Amendment No 20 Act 2013:16). Zimbabwe shares borders with South Africa to the south, Zambia to the north, Mozambique to the east and Botswana and Namibia to the west.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: MCZ Handbook, 2023. The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe handbook. Harare: Connexional Bookshop.
- Source 2: Constitution of Zimbabwe Amendment No 20 Act, 2013. Harare: Fidelity Printers.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.afrigis.co.za>
- Source 1 Description: AfriGIS is the source where the map was drawn from.
- Source 2 URL: Martin Mujinga <https://www.semanticscholar.org>
- Source 2 Description: The sources written by this Methodist scholar gives much information to this entry for the first reader
- Source 3 URL: Peter Masvotore. <https://www.semanticscholar.org>
- Source 3 Description: The articles and publications by the scholar are a rich source to the understanding of Methodism in Zimbabwe

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

- Yes

Notes: The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe through its various groups namely Ruwadzano/Manyano (Women's fellowship), Men's Christian Union (MCU), and Youth groups such as Methodist Young Disciples (MYD), Boys Christian Union (BCU), Girls Christian Union (GCU), Young Adults (YA) and Sunday school are in cultural contact with the Christian ethos in upholding the Christian values and belief systems enunciated by John Wesley the founder of Methodism in Zimbabwe.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

- Yes

Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

- No

Assigned by personal choice:

- Yes

Notes: According to the Deed of Church order and Standing Orders (2022:249) 900, membership to the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe is for "all those who confess Jesus Christ as Lord and Saviour and accept the obligation to serve Him in the life of the Church and the world are welcome as full members of the Methodist Church. If not baptized already those seeking membership shall be baptized before received as full members." In the Church those who are members are committed to worship, Holy Communion, prayer and Bible study and responsible giving.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: All gender are welcome and in leadership positions there is no segregation

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Notes: Free for all with no conditions attached

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: Through the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe pillar number one that of 'improving Church growth' (MCZ Handbook 2023:2) the evangelism and discipleship committee consider ways of making the Christian faith meaningful and relevant to those outside the church (Deed of Church order and Standing orders 2022:74). It is also this evangelistic thrust that saw missionaries coming in 1891 to the then Rhodesia now Zimbabwe for the purpose of propagating the gospel to the people of Zimbabwe. When the missionaries the likes of Owen Witkins, Isaac Shimmin and others had to cross the frontiers across the Limpopo to Zimbabwe without any military force to protect them serve for God who was their shepherd. Missionaries saw that the work of evangelisation needed indigenous people to spread the good news and for better communication, evangelists from South Africa were sent the likes of Michael bowen, Josiah Ramushu, Basuto Mustualo, Modumedi Moleli, Samuel Tutani, Wellington Belisi, James Anta and others who became instrumental in the evangelization process (Mujinga 2017:117). The organisations in the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe have a mandate to grow the Church numerically through recruiting new members.

Reference: Mujinga, Martin. *The Historical Development of Methodism A North-south Paradigm*. Harare: Connexional Bookshop, 2017.

Reference: MCZ, ed.. The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe Agenda of the 46th Conference 2023. Edited by MCZ. Harare: Connexional Bookshop, 2023.

Reference: MCZ, ed.. The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe Handbook. Edited by MCZ. Harare: Connexional Bookshop, 2023.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: From the on set Methodist Church in Zimbabwe worked hand in glove with those who were champions of political power. Watkins the first missionary worked together with Cecil John Rhodes to secure the mission farms. It was because of cordial relations that Watkins was given three farms to start with more than other churches could secure and he was promised more if the mission was a success (Watkins 1891).

Reference: "Watkins Private Journal", 1891.

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: In the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe since one chooses to be a member willingly the chances of apostasy are very slim if not none.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 123262

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 55

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible is written source where Methodists use for preaching

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– Yes

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The Scriptures are not alterable in the sense of removing what one deems not necessary but through translations meaning may be lost and through exegesis one may interpret the Scriptures to suit their context.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: United Theological College is one of the institutions that has the responsibility to train ministers of religion in Zimbabwe. during ministerial formation the students are exposed to Biblical exegesis, Interpretation and Application.

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

Notes: Scriptures were translated into vernacular languages first from their original languages from Hebrew (Old Testament) Greek (New Testament) into English first and Ndebele as languages spoken by the majority of the population under study.

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Although monuments are there like John Wesley's statue, Methodist Church in Zimbabwe does not put much focus and attention to religious relics instead the focus is on the risen Christ instead of religious monuments.

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage: 10

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 100

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 35

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Height, square meters: 100

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 35

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Percentage of area: 60

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– Yes

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Tents

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

– All public spaces

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Yes

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc..

– Yes

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: Believers in traditional afterlives strongly believe they continue to have consciousness experiences after death via their souls. Interalia magazine <https://www.interaliomag.org>

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: This is in line with our African culture where there is belief that the spirit has inherent powers

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

- ↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The two co-exist in harmony. They are inseparable. When they separate then death is the result

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The explanation given is to give hope to believers that those who receive grace shall live an eternal life.

- ↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "below" space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– Yes

Notes: In this space it is assumed that when one dies the spirit may be lingering in the horizontal space before judgement. This could be seen through alien spirits or medium spirits that may even possess the living and perform some healing and guiding the living. When one is possessed one is heard saying "I am from a far away place, a place that is very hot" and some may demand water to drink signifying that the spirit could be in the horizontal space somewhere.

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: The belief in reincarnation also appears in the religious and philosophical thought of local religions in Africa and the Methodist Church does not explicitly talk of reincarnation as a denomination but there are members within this church who are traditionalists who perhaps carries the notions of African traditional beliefs and they have a dual membership.

↳ In a human form:

– Yes

↳ In animal/plant form:

– Yes

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– Yes

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– Yes

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– Yes

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: Resurrection

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: The Methodist Church has respect to the dead as such the corpse of the departed is given the last respect through performances of rituals that befits one's standing in the church in honour of the contribution one has done to the church.

↳ Cremation:

– Yes

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– Yes

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: sideways

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

↳ Feeding to animals:

– Yes

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– Yes

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Embalment

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: Sacrifices comes in form of rituals that are performed during burial following a designed liturgy for burial of the members of the church. Contributions are also paid to the surviving spouse or family members as part of what is called "chema" or our tears to the family.

↳ Human sacrifices present:

– No

Notes: There are no sacrifices in form of human sacrifices because only Jesus is worth the sacrifice for all who have sinned and he is the ransom payment to our sins.

↳ Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Notes: In some cultures they kill a cow at the funeral of an elder. The cow is shown to the members of the family and "muzukuru will show the relatives "usavi hwagadzirwa kuti vanhu vacheme nekuperekedza mufi" (the meat to be prepared as people mourn the deceased)

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: This also depends on different cultures where the MCZ serve. In other places there should be reeds, a mat or some utensils that will accompany the deceased during the burial process. They have different significance according to different cultures. It is not the obligation of the church to look for such goods but if the families so wish to have such things then the minister presiding over the burial ritual will not challenge them.

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: This is solely on the beliefs of different people due to difference in cultures and customs which are accomodated by the church.

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Again it all depends with family beliefs and cultures. For the church to be effective it has to adapt to the living cultures of the areas where it operate.

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– Yes

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– Yes [specify]: Utensils

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Formal burials are present and they follow prescribed liturgy in the MCZ.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: These are done as memorial services to those who perished in diaspora or during the war. Monuments are erected in their memory. Sometimes buildings are built as memorial monuments in our churches.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: There are different types of cemeteries. Some are family cemeteries, some are village or communal cemeteries. The MCZ has also gone to the extent to establish sites for cemeteries in its mission farms and at some church premises there are grave yards for cemeteries.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Inscriptions are written on tombs and the MCZ during performing the rites of passage in tombstone unveiling they give time for the reading of the inscription to the family.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic

activities):

– Yes

Notes: Although this may happen it is rarely practised by members of the MCZ.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Some are taken to their rural homes where they are buried at designated family burial sites

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: This is a phenomenon that is prevalent in the African culture where the MCZ predominantly operate.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: From an African Traditional point of view they are present and is in control.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Is usually ascribed to dwell in the sky, but has control in this world and the underworld. In terms of dwelling place the supreme high god is ascribed to dwell in the sky with influence to both the underworld and this world.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– Yes

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Loving and forgiving

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The fact that this is one of the attributes of the supreme God it therefore cascade even to the deities of this world.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: All knowing and goes beyond human comprehension

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The supreme god has foreknowledge to know what shall happen in future. The MCZ teaches about prophecies as what happened in the Bible.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Knowledge about death and the eschaton

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: As long as one has supremacy it therefore means that there is causality in this world and beyond.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– No

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Adherents are encouraged to worship one supreme high god only in the MCZ

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Angelic features and that which is beyond human recognition

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: The ability to communicate in whatever form and through any means is vested in the supreme being to the living of this world

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through nature and indigenous knowledge systems

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: It is a fact that spirits are present in this world. they manifest physically, they are felt and they cause prosperity and even misfortunes to the inhabitants especially from an African point of view.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - Yes [specify]: They operate through the Supreme being who gives knowledge beyond
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: They take any form of shape

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

↳ Through divination processes:

– Yes

↳ Only through specialists:

– Yes

↳ Only through monarch:

– Yes

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: Through visuals and dreams

– Yes

Notes: In Africa spirits do communicate through human beings and other vessels they may choose to possess.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: From the stand point of the MCZ as an indigenous church operating from

African human spirits have knowledge of this world as testified by the spirit medium of mbuya nehanda and sekuru Kaguvi who are the spirit mediums of the Zimbabwean nation. All the underneath statements are a yes because there is a strong belief in the spirit medium who knows beyond this world and even in the darkest echelons of life.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– Yes [specify]: They know about afterlife

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: They can reward and punish at the same time. Reward when one does well and when they are pleased but punish as a way to refocus the person or to give a strong warning.

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: May possess animal features

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: As alluded earlier on communication do take place in all forms

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

- ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
- ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
- ↳ Through divination processes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through specialists:
 - Yes
- ↳ Only through monarch:
 - No
- ↳ Communicate with living through other means:
 - Yes [specify]: signs

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: These do exist in this world and the underworld.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

- No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

- Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

- Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

- No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Afterlife

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: It could be so since they are supernatural beings.

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:
 - Yes [specify]: Since they are supernatural they do have knowledge regarding this world.
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Extraordinary features beyond human recognition.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
 - Yes [specify]: Afterlife knowledge
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes

- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Extraordinary features

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In waking, everyday life:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In dreams:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In trance possession:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Through divination practices:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through religious specialists:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Only through monarch:
 - Yes

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through nature and signia

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be seen:

– Yes

↳ These mixed human-divine beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings have other knowledge of the human world:
 - Yes [specify]: Yes they are all knowing
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ These mixed human-divine beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: since they are mixed human divine they can possess some unique

features that are beyond explanation

↳ Mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living:
– Yes

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– Yes

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: This is true because we have a God who sees every where and one has to account for the life lived at the end of this world.

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:
Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
– Yes

Notes: Taboos are part of indigenous knowledge system that helps society to preserve it natural

environment as well as keeping its social norms and traditional values.

↳ Food:
– Yes

↳ Sacred space(s):
– Yes

↳ Sacred object(s):
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:
– Yes [specify]: other living human beings

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
– Yes
Notes: The MCZ is against shedding of blood in what ever way hence one should not kill

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
– Yes
Notes: The supernatural being monitors and advocate for pureness both in body and in spirit.

↳ Adultery:
– Yes

↳ Incest:
– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:
– Yes [specify]: infidelity

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Truthfulness is one characteristic of the deity as such it guard against telling lies. The MCZ has truthfullness as one of its virtue and value.
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: prosperity

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: It is our belief that they initiate punishment as a way of a deterrent measure to humanity

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: In African Traditional Religion where MCZ operate there is a cause to every punishment that can be attributed to disobedience to the Almighty.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The high god punishes believers as a way to show power and to deter them to do good always and learn lessons from the eventuality.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Sometimes it is known and in other times believers will sought answers from the practitioners who will tell them the reasons as form of prophecy.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: Religious devotional adherence is enhanced through availing reasons for supernatural punishment as is always seen when members are disciplined in the MCZ

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: For a special purpose

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: This is probable as said by the Bible that there shall be punishment to those who are found wanting at the end of this world

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: This is done in the MCZ as a corrective measure and warning to the members so that they live a life worth rewarding by God.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: This could be an assumption since no one has ever experienced such a life.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:
– Yes

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:
– Yes

Notes: There are certain incidents that occur in life that points to the punishments from the supernatural. The MCZ as earlier on indicated it believe in both realised and future eschatology hence some of the eventualities are witnessed here and now while others are in the here and after.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:
– Yes

Notes: Emphasis is given as a way to teach believers to be on the ideal side rather than conform to the worldly standards.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:
– Yes

Notes: Bad luck is attributed to a form of punishment that is here and now instead of waiting for the future.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes

Notes: Traditionally and from the perspective of the MCZ crop failure and bad weather could be the answer or form of communication from God sending a signal to humanity to repent and do good.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes

Notes: When one embarks on a journey the first thing is to pray for journey mercies. When one encounter disaster on a journey the interpretation could be that "midzimu

yadambura mbereko" meaning that the ancestors have torn the baby towel. When this usually happens one should not take it lightly but to pray for a breakthrough.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
Notes: This could be a signal for misfortunes and calamities ahead.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:
– Yes
Notes: This teaching is no longer strong today where there is much talk of theology of inclusion. That which accomodates people regardles of impairment

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:
– Yes
Notes: Some other ministers in the MCZ, those who call themselves prophetic pastors do pray for people to cast out bad luck that could be generational.

↳ Other [specify]
– Yes
Notes: bad omen

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Rewards are what Christians are waiting and working for in this world and the life after this world.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:
– Yes

Notes: Through the teachings from the Bible and through the homilies received there is an anticipation that the rewards are known as living a better life free from challenges of this world.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: God is the source of all good things

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: When permitted and acting as agents of the most high God they can reward.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: As a matter of principle and enforcement of good morals and values.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

↳ Done randomly:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: It is not only in the afterlife but also in this life and the life to come as future eschatology.

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: As a way to foster discipline and values in the church and to also encourage people to have hope as religious pundits

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: This is what is anticipated by most believers in the MCZ

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– Yes

Notes: This is not directly contained in the Bible but general view of believers has that assumption which is difficult to prove although it helps believers to persevere.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– No

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Yes some are rewarded as they do good things in this life as a lesson to the believers today

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The MCZ in particular do emphasize on the rewards in whatever form be it success i business, political carrer and even in the yields during harvest etc.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: This could be to those that did good while living here on earth.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Prosperity

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The MCZ has a strong belief in both the realised and the future eschatology as emphasized in its teachings and doctrines.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: Although the specific Chronos time is not known but the kyros time where people wait

for the opportune time and are ready for anything

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: Through the teachings of the MCZ and the Bible people get to have an idea on the purpose of the messiah in this life and afterlife.

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Redemption of the universe

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: realised eschatology

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– Yes [specify]: Unknown time

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– Yes

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

↳ Other survival condition:

– Yes [specify]: Those that are faithful to God

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: There are guiding principles and orders that are adhered to by members of the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe particularly in religious groups such as Manyano, MCU. The general guiding rules and orders are enshrined in the Deed of Church order and Standing Orders.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– Yes

- ↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
 - Yes
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
 - Yes
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
 - Yes
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
 - Yes
- ↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
 - Yes

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - Only specialized religious class
 - All individuals within society (excepting slaves, aliens)
 - All individuals within society
 - All individuals within contemporary world
 - All individuals (any time period)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: MCZ, ed.. The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe Agenda of the 46th Conference 2023. Edited by MCZ. Harare: Connexional Bookshop, 2023.

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - No
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes

- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
– Yes
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
– Yes
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
– Yes
- ↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:
– Yes
- ↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:
– Yes
- ↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:
– Yes
- ↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:
– Yes
- ↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:
– Yes
- ↳ Fidelity / loyalty:
– Yes
- ↳ Cooperation:
– Yes
- ↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:
– Yes
- ↳ Moderation / frugality:
– Yes

- ↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:
– Yes
- ↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:
– Yes
- ↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes
- ↳ Strength (physical):
– Yes
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
– No
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Yes
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
– Yes
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Yes
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Yes
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Yes
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:
 - Yes [specify]: soberness

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Members are allowed to marry. Partners may choose to abstain perhaps if they are on fasting but that has to be on mutual agreement.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Fasting is required depending on one's volution and choice. Programmes like the Covenant month at the beginning of every year in January the church organises some 10 to 30 days of prayer and fasting which is not obligatory but open to those who are willing.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: There is no restriction on what one should eat save for drinking of alcohol and taking of illegal substances such as drugs.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: These are not necessary since Christ has endured all the pain on our behalf (Hebrews 2:9-10; 1 Peter 4:13).

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No human sacrifice is worthy atoning for one's sins serve for what Christ has done already on the cross.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: This is not required at all because it is not a cultic religion. Instead it is against the laws of the country and against the right to life as advocated by the children's rights.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: Taking one's life is considered an act of desperation and one has to seek counselling to avoid such a sinful action.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: In our circumstance it might be regarded as voluntary giving without any punishment to those who may fail to give. There are membership fees or contributions that are collected and these are subject to audit by a professional registered finance institution. All monies contibuted are given to the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe and not to an individual. Upon giving to the church one is given an official receipt as proof of contribution

↳ To other in-group members:

– No

↳ To out-groups:

– No

↳ Destroyed:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: There is need for members to commit themselves voluntarily towards attending meetings and prayer sessions which could be in form of All night prayers and crusade etc.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Ethical precepts such as avoiding taking life, avoiding taking what is not given etc are essential in Christianity particularly in the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe as guiding principles for the community.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Notes: Methodist Church in Zimbabwe has inclusivity as one of its values where it has gone to establish a safeguarding and gender desk to protect the vulnerable groups (MCZ Handbook 2023:6).

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Notes: Rituals that are done in the Methodist Church in Zimbabwe are guided and are performed during Holy Communion and Baptism services.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 1

Notes: These are performed within a worship service which takes one hour to complete

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 50000

Notes: It depends with the type of gathering. If it is Easter celebration it takes more than 50000

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 5

Notes: These large scale gatherings happen after every 5 years

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe like earlier indicated is located in Zimbabwe which is a sovereign state.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe has its arm the Methodist Development and Relief Agency (MeDRA) which has the responsibility to source for relief items that is then distributed to needy communities regardless of which church one is affiliated to. It has been active during the Cyclone Idai, the Covid-19 pandemic where distribution of goods and services were done to areas affected with famine. <https://www.methodistchurchinzimbabwe.org/departments/index.html>

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Members also receive famine relief through other voluntary organisations like SAVE the Children, Christian CARE etc

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Like indicated elsewhere above the MeDRA department provide poverty relief in the church

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: There are homes that are run by the church to take care of these groups the likes of Matthew Rusike childrens home and Old People's home care.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Voluntary organisations and volunteers as well as well wishers donate to the elderly through the church or direct.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe provide formal education through running of institutions like schools and tertiary institutions as a mission imperative. It also provides training to its preachers and new believers.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The Church has an all inclusive approach and access to education is for all.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Notes: In some societies or circuits they have what is called "Lord's Acre" where people plant crops and harvest to feed those that are in need of help in communities.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through MeDRA the Church has programmes for water harvesting where they provide tanks to communities and some times drill boreholes but the water is for domestic purposes only.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The Methodist Church in Zimbabwe does not necessarily levy taxes but members voluntarily give their tithes and other offerings willingly without any coercion.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: There are moments where the Church inquire or seek guidance from State Judiciary system.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: The Church is guided by the Deed of Church Order and Standing Orders Revised Version 2022.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The State military has the mandate to protect its citizens under which all church members are under the armpit of state security.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Church is guided by the Christian Calendar cycle where the church develops its own handbook that has all important activities and events that will take place in each specific quarter.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Notes: The Church runs commercial farms and its adherents are into small scale farming activities.

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

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